

Learning Experiences from Digital Factory Subject and Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders Subject

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Abstract

The Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0) is a project that develops knowledge and skill necessary for the industrial 4.0, which consists of 16 courses. At present, the Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok (KMUTNB) has already conducted 2 courses, which are Digital Factory subject and Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject. The main objective of this study is to present teaching and learning activities including feedbacks from the courses, which are attended by instructors and 14 students in Master's degree and international exchange students. It also presents experiences from student's perspective, by using indicators in the form of interviews and evaluations. The results are that students can satisfy with the subjects. In addition, they have developed knowledge and skills necessary for the industry 4.0 as intended.

Keywords: Digital Factory; Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders; Industry 4.0; Learning Experiences.

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0 creates new demands on the competencies in connection with the digitalization of future production. The requirements and opportunities, in the use of emerging technology, increase the pressure on the qualification and recruitment of employees with new cognitive skills (Helge, Kurt, & Ib, 2020). From this situation, The Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0) (Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union) has created a course curriculum to develop learners according to the characteristics of industry 4.0. At present, the Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok has a group of students, who have studied Digital Factory subject (MSIE-06) and Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject (MSIE-16). The learning courses are developed for preparing students to the industry 4.0 factories and for responding to current and future smart factory personal needs. In this paper, it summarizes the activities that occur during the pilot courses and the outcomes.

2 The Course Element

2.1 Course Background

Industry expectations of engineering graduates are increasingly expanding with modern times (Evert, 2017). Therefore, the curriculum structure is built on required skills and knowledge in Industry 4.0. The surveying is from the academicians and industrial entrepreneurs' perspectives. The curriculum Development of Master's degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0) has improved the teaching and learning methods which have the structure of the curriculum in 16 courses according to the skills needed for industry 4.0.

2.2 Learning Method: Digital Factory subject

Industry 4.0 requirements can be summarized as flexibility, increased productivity, individual product manufacturing, knowledge and application of new technologies with manufacturing systems and robot

collaboration. These requirements are essential for the future education system (Andrea, Martin, Frantisek, & Jiri, 2019). Therefore, the instructors must redesign their courses in active learning for balancing the learner experiences. The four main dimensions for assessment framework are learning (L), observing (O), visiting (V), and experimenting (E). These dimensions are grouped and named as LOVE model which can be classified for teaching and learning method to balancing the student learning experiences (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya, & Koomsap, 2019). The LOVE model is the important tool for learning experiences based on teaching and learning method (Kengpol, Koohathongsumrit, & Meethom, 2019).

During the teaching process, the students learn related case studies, for example the functional drink industry and the cosmetic packing industry. In the functional drink industry, the decision support system software is developed for assessing customer satisfaction on functional beverage flavor note (Ouansri, Kengpol, Tuamee & Tabkosai, 2020). In the cosmetic packing industry, the production process is improved for reducing the scrap (Mingsakul, Kengpol, Usadornsak & Tuntitippawa, 2020). In addition, there are more case studies for learning and practicing on how to improve the factories and industries.

2.3 Learning Method: Communications and People Skills Developments for Engineering Leaders subject

The evolution of communication relates to the use of linguistic process. Most institution will be likely preferred to embrace a more revolutionary attack by changing the underlying foundation of their educational approach to a new approach of learning utilizing a student-centered strategy (Halizah, & Zawawi, 2015). This subject is an activity-based course. During the lecture sessions, class discussion is conducted. During workshop session, the students are active learners for practicing the communication skills together with the related people skills, and for understanding of the general characteristics of engineering leaders. This course also creates awareness of obstacles to career success when the skills are not developed.

2.4 The Questionnaire and The Interview

Questionnaires can be effective tools for collecting the information, but only if they are properly designed and used. There are a number of factors that should be considered when designing the questionnaire (Tiina, 2006). The 5-level satisfaction questionnaire is commonly used to collect data, which consisted of the average score criteria and interpret the result as follows (Samakpol, 2014):

- The average score of 4.21-5.00 means that the appropriateness is at the highest level
- The average score of 3.41-4.20 means that the appropriateness is at high level
- The average score of 2.61-3.40 means that the appropriateness is at moderate level
- The average score of 1.81-2.60 means that the appropriateness is at low level
- The average score of 1.00-1.80 means that the appropriateness is at the lowest level

The interview is a conversation for gathering information. A research interview involves an interviewer, who coordinates the process of the conversation and asks questions. Interviews can be conducted face-to-face or over the internet/telephone.

3 Learning Activities

This section presents learning activities from the Digital Factory (MSIE-06) and the Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders (MSIE-16) course, which occurred at the Department of Industrial Engineering in King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok. The students from master degree and exchange students from Indonesia and Jordan are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

Figure 1. The students join the courses.

Figure 2. The exchange students from Indonesia and Jordan.

3.1 Digital Factory subject

In the first semester of 2019 between June and October, the students had taken the Digital Factory course (MSIE-06). In the first lesson, the lecturer described the course syllabus including objectives, contents and evaluations, causing the learner to know how to prepare to study. The LOVE model is applied in the course.

The Learning method (L) in the course, the students learn the digital factory by videos playing, and after that they have to express their opinion to exchange the ideas together. Moreover, they have to find information from the internet and have some discussion about the digital factory topics such as the future wind power from smart wind generator, the future farm and the smart assembly plant etc., which is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The Learning (L) activities.

The Observing method, the students try to find interesting new technology from the internet. The cyber-physical system and another type of smart equipment systems such as robotic system, additive manufacturing, automated guided vehicle (AGV), virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) are discussed in the class and

they talked about how to transform a traditional factory to a digital factory. The data flow diagram (DFD) is used to explain how the transformation can be done. The activities are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Observing (O) activities.

The Visiting method in the course, they have first factory visit at the furniture factory as show in Figure 5 for observing the five production lines and writing the Data Flow Diagram (DFD) for group works, and they have to use the knowledge from the learning method and observing method to design the new DFD in each production lines, which can transform to become a digital factory.

Figure 5. The Visiting (V) activities: the first factory visit.

The second factory visit, the students present the ideas in form of DFD for improving each production line to achieve the goal of digital factory. There was a discussion of exchanged ideas between learners and production supervisors about the necessity and possibilities of the new DFD and the related smart equipments in presentation as presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The Visiting (V) activities: the second factory visit.

The Experiment method (E) from the course, the students have joined the virtual reality (VR) laboratory at KMUTNB. They learn VR theory and learn how VR can be applied. The VR goggles are used by the students for grabbing and throwing objects in the virtual world in the laboratory and the students can also see their activities on the screen, as presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The Experiment (E) activities: using VR goggles.

3.2 Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject

In the second semester of 2019, the students had taken the Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders course (MSIE-16). The course objective is to build engineering competence in leadership communication skills and people skills. Thus, the training method is very important so that the students can communicate effectively at the end of the course.

The course has three modules. The module 1 is Essential Communication Skill Development for Self-Expression. The students are improved in oral communication and written communication skills. They practiced by plotting their ideas, filling up and polishing the story respectively. After that, they have to practice the story presenting by video recording themselves when they are presenting the story. The videos from the students are played in the class and the instructor advises to fix weaknesses and skills development guideline for each student. The activities are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Student introductory skills.

The module 2 is Collaborative Communication Skills Development. The students practiced more communication skill such as emotional intelligence, strategic persuasive communication and effective managerial communication in a meeting. The topic of this session training is job application. Hypothetical, the students are finding the new job and try to introduce themselves for applying a job. The training activities is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Student training in classes.

The module 3 is Leadership Communication Skill Development. The students are knowing the leadership style, and they could adapt their communication to different situations and audience.

3.3 Evaluation form

In this study, the evaluation is used to assess appropriateness in Digital Factory subject and the Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject. The students in these courses have to rate the class questionnaires using the appropriate evaluation forms, which the score 5 means strongly appropriate degree, score 1 means weak appropriate degree. The average scores are the result. In addition, the interviews are performed to assess students' experienced and what they gained from the courses.

4 Result

This session presents the student's experience after attending in the Digital Factory Course and Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders course according to interview result and evaluation average scores respectively.

4.1 Digital Factory Course

This subject is using the presentation and the interview to assess student's ability. From the furniture factory visiting in session 3.1, the student presented how to transform the tradition factory to the digital factory, in which the production supervisors attended the presentation. After that, the supervisor conducted additional interviews with the students to assess the knowledge and skill necessary for Industrial 4.0. The result show that, the students have knowledge and skills necessary to create concepts for transforming the tradition factory into the digital factory.

From the student's perspective to this subject, the satisfactory score is used, and the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The assessment of satisfactory score for the Digital Factory subject

No.	Assessment:	Average
1	I learned a lot from this course.	4.42
2	You would recommend the course to other students.	4.58
3	Overall, I am satisfied with the course.	4.67
4	The grades issued were objective and fully reflected the learning outcomes.	4.33
5	The course was conducted in a way that was understandable, interesting, orderly, motivating to learn, and forcing to thinking.	4.50

The average score on all assessments is in the range 4.21-5.00, that means the satisfactory of every assessment is at the very high level.

4.2 Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders course

This subject estimate student's ability by assessing the quality of the speaking skill and the writing skill by the lecturer. The result show that, the students have the skills necessary to communicate on the various occasions, and they know how to improve their communication skills even better.

From the student's perspective to this subject, the satisfactory score is used, and the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The assessment of satisfactory score for the Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject

No.	Assessment:	Average
1	I learned a lot from this course.	5.00
2	You would recommend the course to other students.	4.75
3	Overall, I am satisfied with the course.	5.00
4	The grades issued were objective and fully reflected the learning outcomes.	4.50
5	The course was conducted in a way that was understandable, interesting, orderly, motivating to learn, and forcing to thinking.	4.75

The average score on all assessments is in the range 4.21-5.00, that means the students satisfied with the courses.

From Table 1 and Table 2, the average scores can be shown as a comparison chart as in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Average Satisfactory Scores from Assessment.

5 Conclusions

The students satisfied with both subjects and they have developed skills and knowledge necessary for the Industry 4.0. In which other opinions from the course are as following:

In the viewpoint of students in Digital Factory class, students gained experienced in the form of technology of smart factories in the Industry 4.0. The teaching and learning processes in the subject, the LOVE model has been used effectively. Each class discussions proceeded creatively. The ideas exchanging between the student's workgroups leads to develop the industry 4.0 concepts, that is following global industrial changed.

For the Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders subject, the students practiced communication skills in both speaking and gesture, which can increase communication effectively. The students in the class learned the weaknesses in their communication skills through their videos and practice over and over again to reduce those weaknesses and communicated properly. As for the development of writing skills is proceeded step by step, the students have learned to plot the story line from the milestones and practiced writing for using in various situations effectively.

6 References

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